

ACTIVE PROCESSES IN RUSSIAN WORD FORMATION BASED ON THE LANGUAGE OF MASS MEDIA

PROCESOS ACTIVOS EN LA FORMACIÓN DE PALABRAS DE LA LENGUA RUSA BASADOS EN EL LENGUAJE DE LOS MEDIOS

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RESUMEN

El objetivo de la investigación fue analizar la forma habitual de formación de palabras por afijación en el idioma ruso moderno. Los resultados muestran que los medios de fijación más productivos de la generación de innovación habitual comprenden la formación de palabras por uso de sufijos, ya sea prefijación, sufijo cero y afijo, siendo la más popular la sufijación. Los resultados de nuestra investigación pueden contribuir al desarrollo de la derivación léxica, la semántica léxica, la neología y los problemas estilísticos del lenguaje. El carácter prometedor de la elaboración del tema declarado está condicionado, lo que probablemente requerirá un mayor estudio de los aspectos de la neologización en los textos de los medios de comunicación en un futuro próximo.

Palabras clave: formación de palabras, afijación, afijación cero, neo-nominaciones derivadas,

ABSTRACT

This research aims to analyze the usual form of word-formation by affixation in the modern Russian language. Findings show that the most productive means of affixation comprises the following: suffixation, pre-fixation, zero-suffixation, and affixation-like word formation, being suffixation the most applicable. Our research results can contribute to the development of lexical derivation, lexical semantics, neology, and language stylistics problems. The promising character of elaborating the declared subject is conditioned, which will probably require further analysis of neologization aspects in mass media texts in the nearest future.

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INTRODUCTION

Research on the communicative aspect of word formation and, in particular, neologization in mass media has become one of the most important subjects in the lexical field. Domestic and foreign linguistic writings demonstrate various approaches to derivative lexical studies: structural-semantic (Fatkhutdinova, 2015, Ilyasova, 2016), linguistic and cultural (Erofeeva, 2014, Vendina, 1998), cognitive (Baranov and Dobrovolskij, 1996; Gorobets, Kulsharipova, and Novak, 2016), and methodological (Hashemi, 2011, Martyanov, Gorobets and Novak, 2016). Active derivation processes investigation -based on mass media language and being a kind of catalyst for language transformation- helps to identify critical changes in the word formation system of the Russian language and to trace the trends in usage development as a whole.

The purpose of the present article is to analyze common forms of word formation by affixation as one of the essential operating mechanisms in the Russian language. For that purpose, mass media texts of the last decade as a source for active word-formation processes in the modern Russian language were analyzed.

METHODOLOGY

The research methodology involves the application of linguistic description tools with elements of typical derivative units' interpretation, continuous sampling of lexical materials, structural and semantic word formation analysis, and contextual analysis - at describing the neologisms operation.

The research was carried out on lexical material from newspaper periodicals. The resource base of the research was a corpus that included words extracted from Russian periodical newspapers including: *Argumenty i Fauty*, *Itogi*, *Kommersant*, *Komsomolskaya Pravda*, *Moskovskiy Komsomolets*, *Novaya Gazeta*, *Sovetskiysport*, *Rossiyskaya Gazeta*, and other newspapers.

RESULTS

The language of newspaper periodicals has recently become a sphere of increased word formation activity as it illustrates an enormous number of word derivatives made through the usual word formation methods. Data allowed us to detect the following patterns of word formation that reflect active processes in the modern Russian language: suffix derivation, prefix derivation, and zero suffixation (see figure 1).

1. Derivation by suffixes

As it is known, the morphological derivations can be attained by adding suffixes or prefixes. Suffixation is one of the most popular ways to form new words in the Russian language. It is at the sphere of suffixation where we can observe more

active interaction of 1) borrowed suffixes both with the Russian and foreign word stems; 2) Russian suffixes both with the borrowed and original producing stems; 3) the stylistically heterogeneous morphemic parts: book suffixes and stems in the original stylistically reduced words, and vice versa.

Progress in productivity of several suffixed patterns is noted within the following lexical groups:

1. Names of persons with the meaning of the bearer (subject or processual) formed by:

A) Foreign language productive book suffixes *-uch*, *-amop*, *-ahm* (*-ist*, *-ator*, *-ant*) in conjunction with the foreign and Russian stems: *lobbyist*, *performancist*, *Nashiist* (member of “Nashi” (Ours) organization), *podpisant*, *nominant*, *nominator*, *kommunikator*, and *monetizeator*;

B) Through the Russian suffixes *-ник*, *-чик/-щик*, *-ец/-ов/-овец* (*-nik*, *-chik/-schic*, *-ets/-ov/-ovets*) from non-native stems: *offshornik*, *internetchik*, *piarovets*, *spam-schik*. The semantics of this word subgroup is substantially expanding: in addition to naming of the person by his occupation or interest, they can have the meaning of ‘a supporter, a follower of anything’: *gosudarstvennik* (state authorities’ supporter), *LDPR-ovets* (the supporter of LDPR party), *EGEshnik* (a person who has passed the Uniform State Exam). The forming stem here is often a proper noun combined with the suffix *-ец(-овец)* (*-ets(-ovets)*): *obamovets*, *poroshenkovets*, *zyuganovets*.

Figure 1. Word formation patterns

2. Names with the meaning of an attribute formed through the Russian suffix *-ск, -ов/-оеск, -н* (*-sk, -ov/-ovsk, -n*) combined with the borrowed stems: *schengenskiy, uzerskiy, onlainovyi, piarovskiy, kreativnyi*.

3. Action designations formed by verbal suffixes *-упова, -ова, -у* (*-irova, -ova, -i*):
a) from the borrowed stems of common nouns: *brendirovat', prodyusirovat', kastingovat', offshorit'*; b) from the stems of proper nouns: *gaidarit', chubaisit', naval'nichat', petrosyanit'*.

4. The names of abstract semantics with the Russian suffixes: *-ость/-есть, -ств(о)* (*-ost, -est, -stv(o)*) and borrowed ones: *-изм, -изн, (-ism, -ing)*, their occurrence is connected with the increase in producing stems due to the expansion of colloquialism and jargonism stems existing in the Russian language, foreign stems as well as the use of basic proper names: *pokazushnost', nenashest', zhestokism, lobbism, spamerstvo, premyerstvo, putinism, trampism, marketing, franchising*. The suffix *-ing-* joining the Russian stem (or the stem long ago adapted to the system of the Russian language) performs the function of a game and bears emotional and evaluating character: *pokupping* (shopping), *tovarring, svaling, obyegoring* (screwing over).

5. Designations of socially significant reality processes with the foreign suffixes *-ауuj(a)* and *-изауuj(a)* (*-atsiya, -izatsiya*) derived from a) the borrowed common nouns with the meaning of their baseline: *dollarizatsiya, fermerizatsiya, kompyuterizatsiya*; b) from the personal name stems and expressing the meaning of the process or phenomenon conditioned by the given object activity or influence. Such derivatives acquire expressive and evaluative, but often negative connotation being formed under the influence of both motivating semantics and context (*mavrodi-zatsiya, chubaisizatsiya, navalnizatsiya*).

6. Generated from the Russian stems substantives with the suffixes *-ух(a), -ак, -ач, -ан, -еж, -няк, -щун(a)* (*-ukh(a), -ak, -ach, -an, -ezh, -nyak, -shchin(a)*) generally with a pejorative evaluation, and becoming active in a colloquial sphere. Among them:

- names of abstract semantics: *razvlekukha, golodukha, zhitukha, otkhodnyak, galdyosh*;

- name of persons: *zvezdach, zvezdun, bandyugan, viagrik, stervoza, vypivokha, glupar, parnyaga*;

- designation of phenomena, events, states (*bespredel'shchina, mitingovshchina, obydyonshchina, anomal'shchina*), neologisms occupying a special place among them, being formed from the proper names of the prominent contemporary figures: *luzhkovshchina, kadyrovshchina, poroshenkovshchina, obamovshchina, trampovshchina*.

2. Derivation by Prefixes

One of the productive patterns in present word formation is joining the Russian prefixes to borrowed stems. Recently, the bookish sphere has been enriched by a number of neologisms with foreign prefixes *антi-*, *контр-* (*anti-*, *kontr-*) and the meaning of negation and antithesis: *antikrizisnyi*, *antipremiya*, *kontrevolutsiya*, *kontrelita*; *псевдо-*, *квaзу-* (*psevdo-*, *kvasi-*) – with the semantics of non-genuine and false: *pseudoparad*, *pseudosmysl*, *kvaziperevorot*, *kvaziekspertiza*, *kvazielitnyi*; *супер-*, *мега-* (*super-*, *mega*) – with size-estimating and attitudinal meaning representing the quantitative expression: *superdorogoi*, *superkomfortnyi*, *supermudrost'*, *megasensatsiya*, *megagory*, *megaegzoticheskiy*; *нано-* (*nano-*), indicating the attitude to nanotechnology: *nanoprotezy*, *nanochastitsa*, *nanoasfalt*; *ре-* (*re-*) with the meaning of the previous action iteration: *renovatsiya*, *repost*.

One may say, that we observe the first signs of emerging a new negative prefix *нон-* (*non-*), which is met in few words with non-native stems: *nonfaktor*, *nonfakt*, *nonstandart*, *nonfigurativnyi*.

The following colloquial prefixes have become active: *с-* (*s-*): *skreativit'*, *spionerit'*, *ssrossiyanit'*; *от-* (*ot-*): *otyekhat'* (to leave for a while), *otkserit'*, *ottelefonit'*; *пере-* (*pere-*): *perepiarit'*, *perestakhanovit'* (from *Stakhanov*), *pereshilit'* (from “*shilo*” – bodkin), *peremylit'* (from “*mylo*” – soap) with the meaning “to surpass in some aspect anybody (anything), who (that) is called a motivating base”; *до-* (*do-*): *dopodumat'*, *donumerovat'*; *об-* (*ob-*): *obshutit'*; *пу-* (*pri-*): *prifantazirovat'*, *prikupit'*; *про-* (*pro-*) with the meaning of adherence to something (most often to any political regime): *prorossiyskiy*, *prozapadnyi*, *proamerikanskiy*; *раз-* (*raz-*) with the meaning of eliminating the previous activity results: *razvidet'*, *razmusorit'*.

3. Word formation pattern of zero suffixation

Zero suffixation is one of the productive ways of nominal word formation -the given pattern functions both in spoken and jargon speech. Within the period under analysis the nouns (mostly related to the colloquial and slang lexicon) with the following derivational meanings, appear to be the most demanding: “abstract action” (*vrub*, *otgib*, *otkat*, *razogrev*, *vzлом* (comp.), *oblom*, *otkaz* (*votkaze*), *dozvon*, *prikol*, *razrul*); “the person”: “the person towards action” (*garant*); “the person – attribute bearer” (*nelegal*, *infantil*, *neformal*, *virtual*); “the person – presentive attribute bearer” (*superchel*, *kach*, *chyos*, *fan*); “the object – attribute bearer” (*chernopol*, *bezna*); “abstractive attribute” (*beles'*, *chern'*).

4. Affixed word formation pattern

In recent decade activation of several borrowed affixes has been accompanied by the enhancement of their expressiveness and evaluativity. Thus, a new suffixoid -*geit* (gate) borrowed from the English language and meaning “political scandal” has become widely used in mass media in neologisms, particularly in those creat-

ed from the proper names–toponyms and names of key figures prominent in specific historical periods: *Altaigeit*, *Irangleit*, *Obamageit*, *Kuchmageit*.

In many mass media innovations the prepositional element *нано-* (*nano-*) no longer indicates a minimal size; it implicates negative evaluation of speculative activities concerning new technologies: *nano-что-то-там* (*nano-something*), *nanoscandal*, *nanodeltsy*, *nanoChubais*, *nanorezultaty*.

Alongside with that, some neutral neologisms turn up to be also efficient, for instance, some names with the element *-мейкер* (*-meiker*): *marketmeiker*, *im-idzhmeiker*, *klipmeiker*, *shoumeiker*; also names with the element *медиа-* (*media-*): *mediabusiness*, *mediaaktivy*, *mediaholding*, *mediamagnat*, *mediapokupka*, *mediaprostranstvo*, *mediarynok*, *mediaset'* and, finally, names with the element *-манья* (*maniya*): *kinomaniya*, *pepsimaniya*, *shokoladomaniya*.

DISCUSSION

Active processes in natural affixation word formation are associated with general linguistic changes caused by social, economic, and political transformations. These occurred in the Russian society during the late XX and early XXI centuries, particularly, the so-called democratization and liberalization of the language and weakening of normative rules in linguistic unit formation and usage, the jargonization of the modern Russian language, and the sharp increase in the flow of English borrowings.

News media phraseology actively uses the resources within the system and the norms of the Russian language. In other words, neologisms in newspaper texts are primarily generated by derivational patterns that use productive word formation affixes. In disregard of the avalanche number of new derivational naming units, which resulted from productive formants that remain virtually unchanged, native speakers prefer active patterns already existing in the language system. On the whole, usual modern word-formation remains within the frames of traditionally common ways of word derivation.

CONCLUSIONS

The most productive affixation means of word formation comprise suffixation, prefixation, zero-suffixation, and affixoid word formation, wherein suffixation turns up to be the most popular tool. Therefore, one of the most efficient patterns of modern word formation is joining Russian native affixes to the borrowed stems, where the suffixes are the most demanding. At the present stage of development, word-formative types have become more adaptive. The system of affixation word formation types is so firm that it can easily recycle borrowed stems forming derivatives with the Russian affixes. That being said, Russian stems are actively involved in word formation, i.e., in creating new words according to the efficient patterns.

Such words represent a systemically important property of the Russian word formation: derivational morphology according to productive patterns is contextually conditioned and situation dependent - moreover, data allowed to point out a noticeable activation of foreign language affixes, being the prefixes the most productive ones.

Intending to the personal criterion increase, word formation in mass media text performs not only a nominative function but also expressive and evaluating ones, being the latter more significant to present-day journalism. Neologisms are an effective means to make the text more expressive, and, what is more, they possess evaluativity or tend to acquire it, as their evaluative nature is syntagmatically and contextually conditioned. Word formation turns into effective axiological aid and one of the tools for social assessment in media personalities' oral activity.

Thus, our research has revealed that the present affixation word formation is one of the most important functional and dynamically developing mechanisms in the Russian derivation system.

From the theoretical point of view, the work is of interest in terms of clarifying scientific ideas about word formation as a dynamic aspect of the Russian language. The results of the research can contribute to the development of problems of lexical derivatology, lexical semantics, neology, and language stylistics.

The promising character of the declared subject is conditioned by activation of language processes in mass media, which will probably require further studies in the nearest future concerning word creation aspects in mass media texts. It will also open doors to research on the functional and pragmatic potential of resources for word formation in contemporary Russian language.

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